

A RESEARCH

ON

**THE PATTERN OF MOBILE DEVICE USAGE AND INTERNET ADDICTION AMONG
MEDICAL STUDENTS IN UNIVERSITY OF UYO**

BY

EKPO, ETINKPO ANTHONY

ROBERT, EDIDIONG PETER

EZEKIEL, OFOFON-ONO ENEFIOK

EGWU, HENRY AMARACHUKWU

GOBO, OBUBELEBARA ROSE

SAGBARA, BARIDA CHARLES

EKPE, MIRACLE EYO

UMOH, EKWERE NSIMA

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this research work on “**The Pattern of Mobile Device Usage and Internet Addiction among Medical Students in University of Uyo**” was carried out by;

EKPO, ETINKPO ANTHONY

ROBERT, EDIDIONG PETER

EZEKIEL, OFOFON-ONO ENEFIOK

EGWU, HENRY AMARACHUKWU

GOBO, OBUBELEBARA ROSE

SAGBARA, BARIDA CHARLES

EKPE, MIRACLE EYO

UMOH, EKWERE NSIMA

.....
DR. O. O. MOTILEWA
Supervisor

.....
Prof. U. S. Ekanem
Head of Department

ABSTRACT

Introduction: The widespread use of mobile devices and the internet has changed the way people communicate, obtain information, and spend their free time. Mobile device usage, defined as the amount of time spent on smartphones or tablets, has increased significantly, with young people being the most active users. Medical students, due to the intensive nature of their studies and the need for constant information access, are especially vulnerable to the benefits and drawbacks of mobile device use. The aim of this study was to describe the pattern of internet use and the prevalence of internet addiction among the students.

Methods: The study was a descriptive cross-sectional study of all medical students in the university. A total of 298 was selected across the 6 classes of the medical students using stratified sampling technique. Data were collected using an interviewer administered tool on a computer-based platform.

Result: About 97% of the respondents are using smartphones, others are on tablets and or laptops, Academic activities is the most common use of the mobile device, in 89% of cases whatsapp is the most commonly used platform. The prevalence of addiction is 81.5 % (46.5% mild, 34% moderate and 1% severe) and similar in both sexes. Addiction is associated with long screen time. Negative effect on the academics and study time were identified perceived effect of addiction

Conclusion: Internet addiction is high among the medical students, there is urgently to put intervention in place such as increasing awareness of internet addiction and its effects among the medical students

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CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

1.0 Background

Mobile device usage has increased for all ages, and will continue to increase far into the future. Here, we defined mobile device usage as time spent using a mobile device such as a smartphone or tablet (1). Globally, more than three billion people use the internet daily with young people being the most common users.

The use of mobile devices has increased significantly among medical students, who are recognized for their intense academic schedules and need for constant access to information. This allows easier teaching and learning processes, communication and sharing of information among students and lecturers. The over-reliance on mobile devices by students is likely to lead to addiction.(2)

The Psychologist Mark Griffiths, one of the widely recognized authorities in the sphere of addictive behavior, is the author of the most frequently quoted definition: “Internet addiction is a non-chemical behavioral addiction, which involves human–machine (computer-Internet) interaction”(2) .Internet Addiction is one of the 11 forms of addictive behaviour.(3)

This problem, defined by excessive and compulsive internet use, has the potential to impair medical students' academic performance, social life, mental health, and overall well-being. Exploring the complex interaction between mobile device use and internet addiction among medical students is critical for understanding the impact and devising methods to avoid negative consequences.

There is a wealth of literature demonstrating how common it is for university students to use mobile devices. Junco and Cotten(4) conducted a study that revealed that university students spend an average of eight to ten hours per day engaging with digital technologies, including smartphones and laptops. This high level of engagement is attributed to the multifunctionality and portability of mobile devices, which facilitate communication, information access, and entertainment.

Medical students are increasingly utilising smartphones and tablets to access textbooks, medical apps, and online resources as a result of the growing acceptance of mobile devices in medical education. According to a survey by Payne et al.(5), the majority of medical students are reported using smartphones for educational purposes, highlighting the importance of mobile technology in medical training. Additionally, mobile applications containing clinical case studies, interactive tutorials, and medical reference materials have been developed specifically with medical students in mind.

While mobile devices offer numerous benefits for medical education and clinical practice, they also pose risks of internet addiction and excessive usage. Internet addiction, characterized by compulsive internet use leading to impairment or distress, has emerged as a significant concern among university students. Kwon et al.(6), developed and validated a smartphone addiction scale, underscoring the reliability and validity of tools to measure such addictive behaviors in university populations.

The University of Uyo, located in Nigeria, is home to a diverse student population, including medical students pursuing undergraduate degrees and resident doctors undergoing postgraduate training. Despite the growing recognition of mobile device usage and internet addiction among university students globally, there is a paucity of research focusing specifically on medical students at the University of Uyo. Understanding the patterns of mobile device usage and the prevalence of internet addiction among medical students in this context is essential for developing targeted interventions and support services.

Several factors contribute to the patterns of mobile device usage and internet addiction among medical students. Academic workload, peer influences, and individual characteristics may influence students' digital behaviors and attitudes towards technology. For instance, a study by Yang et al.(7) found gender differences in the association of smartphone use with the vitality and mental health of adolescent students, highlighting the need for gender-specific interventions.

In addition to academic factors, socio-cultural influences may shape mobile device usage patterns among medical students in Nigeria. Cultural norms, socioeconomic status, and access to technology infrastructure may impact students' access to and usage of mobile devices and the internet.

While mobile devices have revolutionized the way medical students learn and communicate, their overuse poses significant risks. Understanding the pattern of mobile device usage and its correlation with internet addiction is essential for developing effective strategies to support students' academic success and mental health. Future research should continue to explore this dynamic, aiming to create a sustainable educational environment where technology enhances rather than hinders student growth.

1.1 Statement of Problem

The growth and development of the smartphone industry has been continuous since 2008, both in market size and in number of models and vendors. Globally, over one billion units were added to smartphone shipments in 2023 alone(8). By the end of 2023, almost 70 percent of the world's population were smartphone owners(9). However, given that many people use more than one smartphone, the actual number of smartphone subscriptions exceeds the number of smartphone users. In 2023, smartphone owners used an estimated seven billion smartphone subscriptions, which is expected to climb to almost eight billion by 2028(10).

On the other hand, it has been estimated that 210 million people worldwide suffer from internet addiction. By gender predisposition, it was shown that 6% of men and 32% of women were addicted to social media(11). The annual growth rate of internet user's is 4.1% (i.e., 196 million people). Average duration of the internet use is 6 hours and 57 minutes per day on connected activities. Younger people tend to spend more time online than older generations do, with young women spending the greatest amount of time using the internet(12). This excessive use of mobile devices and the Internet has resulted in the significant concerns with regards to problematic Internet behaviors and related conditions. Internet addiction (IA) is the lack of ability to control the Internet use and involvement leading to progressive loss of control(13). Similar to behavioral addictions, it poses a series of adverse effects, both to the individual and consequently to the society at large.

Problems may directly affect the individual's physical health as in headaches, neck, and wrist pain, obscured vision. Obvious and latent cognitive disorders have been identified, just as emotional problems such as depression and anxiety have also been reported(14)(15). It has been suggested that though these individuals typically engage in passive social media use, for

example, scrolling through social media news, in an attempt to alleviate the depressive symptoms, they often express feelings of boredom and a lack of pleasure while under continued internet presence. This repetitive, joyless and excessive internet use can develop into a habitual or even compulsive behavior, where depressive symptoms automatically trigger passive internet use, creating a vicious cycle. Unfortunately, inhibiting this impulsive behavior becomes challenging in itself (16). Other psychosocial implications indicated that excessive mobile device usage and internet addiction has a direct effect on bedtime procrastination in a path analysis study, leading to insomnia and daytime sleepiness especially as social media use near bedtime often leads to lack of nighttime routines. Again, excessive smartphone use was found to be adversely associated with self-esteem among young and middle-aged adults as it was shown that there exists an association between excessive smartphone use and an insecure attachment style in problematic adolescent users (17)

On the societal scale, it has been observed that excessive mobile device use and internet addiction could lead to impaired family and school relationships. Therein, Intimate relationships and even work environments can be degraded by internet use, particularly due to viewing online pornographic contents, online grooming and online scams, all of which its susceptibility partly depends on the amount of time spent on the internet. Malicious online behavior, particularly cyber-bullying and cyber-stalking also affects a significant percentage of the internet community.

This study helped to confirm and fill the gap of knowledge among the medical students in (2) some Nigerian Universities, close to two-thirds (59.5%) of them had internet addiction, with (45.4%) having mild addiction, and (14.0%) having moderate addiction; and whether Internet addiction was associated with the use of both mobile data/personal hotspots and College Wi-Fi for internet access and the spending ≥ 6 hours on the internet per day, resulting to excessive internet use with a waste of time and money (22.5%), loss of self-control (19.6%), neglect of social life (11.0%), and neglect of academic work (7.0%) according to Ali Samaila et al. (2022) (34). For the number of hours spent on their respective mobile devices, Shehu et al. stated that the percentage of

time students attributed to different applications varied mildly from their responses. Using the most hours spent on sites per week, (10.2% spend >20 hours) on academic sites, while (6.0% spend > 20 hours) on chatting sites, and (5.7% spend >20 hours) on social networking sites per week(18).

1.2 Justification of Study

Generally, the observed attitudes of students and youths of the present-day generation in the use of mobile devices and internet addiction; including the medical students, especially those of the University of Uyo, is of great concern to parents, school administrators and government at large. Therefore, this study has come at the right time because it would help reveal an evidence-based current trend and pattern of usage of mobile devices and internet addiction with both positive and negative outcomes.

The emphasis of this study was on the medical students because it is a known fact that they spend more time in the duration of their medical training than other students, their study is so crucial because of the unique and tight academic schedule which makes them usually not have the luxury of time for social and non-academic activities, therefore any prolonged addiction in the use of the mobile device and the misuse of the internet would certainly impact negatively on their studies.

Moreover, this study helped to reveal what the trend looks like among the University of Uyo medical students. For instance, some previous studies had shown that a large number of students are addicted to their mobile devices and this had continued with minimal hinderance, in fact, the prevalence in one of the study was discovered to be higher in female medical students than in the males, and the most problematic addictions were aided by the presence of intense desire, impaired control tolerance, and harmful practices of mobile device usage according to Kamal et al. (2022)(14). This study therefore identified addictions based on gender and other characteristics, and then determined the prevalence of mobile device usage and internet addiction among the targeted population, hence contributing to the body of knowledge.

The study showed the impact that the use of mobile devices has on the academic activities of the University of Uyo medical students and how common internet addiction is. The findings from this study can be inferred to other categories of students in the University. It will help policy makers especially school administrators, guidance counselors, lecturers and others to understand the pattern of the use of mobile devices of the university of Uyo medical students. They can also devise means to reduce and prevent the trend of internet addiction, ultimately creating awareness while giving laudable insight on the possible pattern among the other students of the entire university on mobile devices usage and internet addiction.

1.3 Study Objectives

1.3.1 AIM:

To describe the pattern of use and prevalence of internet addiction with the use of mobile devices among medical students in University of Uyo, July 2024.

1.3.2 SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES:

1. To describe the pattern of use of mobile devices among Medical Students in University of Uyo.
2. To determine the prevalence of internet addiction associated with the use of mobile devices among medical students in University of Uyo.
3. To identify factors associated with internet addiction among the medical students.
4. To identify the perceived effects of use of mobile devices on academic performance of medical students in University of Uyo.

1.4 Definition of Terms

1.4.1 Pattern of Usage

The habitual manner in which individuals interact with and utilize a particular technology or device over a period of time. This includes frequency, duration, and context of use.

1.4.2 Mobile Devices

Portable electronic devices that allow users to perform various tasks such as communication, internet browsing, and accessing applications. Examples include smartphones, tablets, and wearable technology.

1.4.3 Addiction

A compulsive need to engage in behaviors or consume substances despite harmful consequences. In the context of internet addiction, it refers to excessive and uncontrollable internet use that interferes with daily life.

1.4.4 Medical Student

An individual enrolled in a medical school or program who is undergoing training and education to become a physician.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

The rapid evolution of technology in the last few decades has significantly impacted various fields, including medicine. Medical students today are increasingly reliant on various medical devices and the internet for their education and practice. While these technologies offer substantial benefits, there is growing concern about their potential negative impacts, particularly regarding internet addiction. A review is done to give an overview of the extent to which medical students depend on these mobile devices and the burden of internet addiction among this group of students. Generally, the pattern of medical device usage and internet addiction among medical students at the University of Uyo reflects broader trends observed globally. While these devices offer significant educational benefits, the risk of internet addiction poses a serious challenge. Addressing this issue requires a balanced approach that maximizes the benefits of technology while mitigating its potential negative impacts. Through effective individual strategies and supportive institutional policies, it is possible to harness the advantages of medical devices while promoting the well-being and academic success of medical students. Further research is needed to develop and refine these strategies, ensuring they are tailored to the specific needs and contexts of medical students at the University of Uyo and beyond.

During this research, we will be using the following terms

Laptops and Tablets

A large proportion of medical education now involves digital resources, including e-books, online journals, and virtual simulations. Laptops and tablets are essential tools for accessing these resources. According to studies, over 90% of medical students regularly use laptops and mobile tablets for educational purposes(19)

Smartphones are everywhere and multifunctional, offering applications that assist in medical calculations, drug information, and communication.(20)

Specialized Medical Equipment

Practical training necessitates the use of devices like stethoscopes, blood pressure monitors, and ultrasound machines. These are integral to the hands-on learning experiences required in medical education.(21)

Pattern of Usage

Aside from using mobile devices for educational purposes it could also be used for other extra-curricular activities such as entertainment and other social activities such as gaming, chatting and even watching movies.

Educational vs. Recreational Use

While the primary use of these devices is educational, there is a significant overlap with recreational activities. The dual-purpose nature of smartphones, in particular, blurs the lines between academic and non-academic use(22)

Time Spent on Devices

Studies have shown that medical students spend an average of 5-6 hours daily on their devices, with a considerable portion of this time devoted to non-academic activities(23)

Academic Pressure

The intense academic workload and pressure to perform can drive students to use the internet excessively as a coping mechanism

Social Isolation

Medical students often experience social isolation due to their rigorous study schedules, leading them to seek social interaction and entertainment online(22)

Impact on Academic Performance and Well-being

Negative Academic Outcomes in terms of procrastination: Internet addiction has been linked to decreased academic performance due to poor time management and procrastination. Where

different studies have shown its impact on lower academic grades among medical students
Academic procrastination of medical students.(24)

Intersection of Medical Device Usage and Internet Addiction: The intersection of medical device usage and internet addiction presents a complex dynamic where the benefits of technology in medical education are potentially undermined by its misuse.

Positive Educational Outcomes

Enhanced Learning Opportunities: The use of digital resources and medical apps has revolutionized medical education by providing instant access to a wealth of information and interactive learning tools.

Improved Diagnostic Skills: Simulation tools and diagnostic apps available on these devices enhance the practical skills of medical students, preparing them better for real-world clinical settings.

2.2 Pattern of Uses Of Mobile Device

A mobile or cell phone is a gadget that transmits voice or data over a long distance across a network of specialized base stations or cell sites. Most mobile phones (MPs) have standard voice capabilities. The current services offered by these include Bluetooth, infrared, text messaging, packet switching, gaming, video recording, e-mail, camera, multimedia message service (MMS), general packet radio service (GPRS), moving picture experts group layer-3 (MP3) player, and radio(19). A corresponding look then at the pattern of mobile device usage in medical colleges across the globe has shown a prevalence of excessive or problematic usage, habits predisposing to a particular pattern and the peculiar demographics affected. The number of smartphone owners and users is predicted to have tripled between 2017 to 2022 as record shows it to have increased from 2.1 billion smartphone users in 2017 to 7.26 billion users in 2022(25). While these trends speak to the general public, it is also reflective of a specific population of youths as it has been noted that some of the main factors predicting excessive mobile device use are preoccupation, conflicts, female gender, use for ubiquitous traits and young age (26).

Smetaniuk reported that young age, depression and extroverted disposition were risk factors to smartphone addiction(27). The average Korean smartphone addiction scale score was significantly higher in youths than any other age bracket. It was also higher in women than in men (41.30 vs 37.94 $p=0.001$) (26). Another demographic characterization of problematic mobile users was by classifying them into a non-addictive group, a problematic use group and an addictive group by means and standard deviation(28). However, more recent classifications using analytical forms like Latent Profile Analysis (LPA) which itself is a form of Latent class analysis tend to assess continuous indicators using an empirically derived approach for revealing unobserved heterogeneity in a population. This is by identifying different categories of participants within a given sample(29). To quantitatively assess participants' mobile phone use levels, the Mobile Phone Addiction Index Scale was used. This considers four dimensions, including inability to control cravings, feeling anxious and lost, withdrawal or escape, and loss of productivity. Using this scheme, Cui et al. came to the conclusion that problematic social media use (PSMU) is heterogeneous, with depression and stress being the key influential factors. They grouped this problematic social media use into high risk PSMU, moderate risk with compulsion PSMU, moderate risk with pleasure PSMU, low risk PSMU(30).

Recruited for a study by Msuega et al. were a total of 147 medical students at Benue State University (BSU), Makurdi, made up of 107(72.8%) males and 40 (27.2%) females. A good number, 55 (37.4%) of the students were in their 4th year of study, followed by 51 (34.7%) in the 5th year, with the final (6th) year students having the least number of 41(27.9%). A background to the participants' responses to inquiries about mobile phone usage revealed that all 147(100%) respondents own and make use of mobile phones, with a male to female ratio (M: F) of nearly 3:1. Sixty-seven (62.6%) males and 30 (75.0%) females have at least one mobile phone. Sixty-one (41.5%) students have used mobile phones for 6–10 years, with only 3(2.0%) having used the device for under one year. The 3 most popular phone brands were Techno, Infinix and Samsung with a consecutive frequency of 46(31.3%), 22(15.0%) and 15(10.2%). Among the males, 34(31.8%), 14(13.1%) and 9(8.4%) commonly make use of Techno, Infinix and Samsung consecutively, while 12(30.0%), 8(20.0%) and 6(15.0%) females frequently use the same 3 brands. Ninety-three (63.3%) students were aware of the potential health risks associated with MP usage; 30 (20.4%) highly aware, 40 (27.2%) aware, and 23 (15.7%) slightly aware. The successive ranges of 1.00 - 1.75, 1.76 - 2.5, 2.51 -3.25 and 3.26 - 4.00 (unaware, slightly aware,

aware, highly aware) and the average mean of 2.7, which falls within the 2.51-3.25 range is suggestive that the predominant response is "aware". The 3 most potential health risks, to which the predominant response was "highly aware" are the eye problems, increased risks of road traffic accident (RTA) and headaches with a frequency of 61(41.5%),61(41.5%) and 49(33.3%) whereas pimples were the least item(19). In an independent research carried out by Bello and Raji in Obafemi Awolowo university, they found out that 80% of the respondents with sophisticated phones bought them as refurbished phones due to the cheap price. 40% of new phones are specifically made for the Nigerian market. 60 % of the respondents who have a relatively high maximum call time per day of continuous 5 minutes and above were basically within the age range 20-29 years using free night call offers. The analysis shows 63.7% basically do more of calling, 77.5% on other online activities like gaming, browsing, ping, chatting, etc. While the 80.1% majority of respondents, usually place Mobile phones close to the ears, 12.5% usually use hands-free, 6.5% on speaker phones and 0.9% do not have a specific routine. 42.5% of the respondents make use of Bluetooth devices for various mobile phone activities, against the 57.5% that do not make use of the device. It is of interest to note that a non-significant of the student's populace 0.02%, do not own a mobile phone while 40.2% have more than a mobile phone(14).

Likewise, another research in Ogun state showed that most respondents (80.7% during the week and 82.6% during the weekend) spent between 10 and 20 hours studying on electronic devices, 82.1% during the week and 77.8% during the weekend spent between 10 - 20 hours doing job or internship-related work, and 71.8% during the week and 28.2% during the weekend spent between 10 - 20 hours watching entertainment programs. The Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index was used to assess the impact of screen exposure on respondents' health and it revealed that less than a third (29.8%) normally go to bed between 10:00 PM and 10:59 PM, while 64.1% require more than 60 minutes to fall asleep each night. 39.3% wake up between 5:00 and 5:59am, whereas 35.9% sleep for 6-7 hours. 63.6% of respondents had not had any sleep therapy in the previous month, and 80.5% reported no difficulty staying awake when driving, eating meals, or engaging in social activities. Again, the respondents' level of screen addiction as measured by the multiple screen addiction scale. It revealed that 54.1% of respondents frequently have a busy mind while using one or more displays. 47.5% occasionally spend more time with any screen than planned, 62.8% frequently cannot control the time spent in front of any screen showed that

78.1% frequently cannot tolerate not having access to screen, and 61.2% frequently check the screens even when no work or purpose is available. The most common activity 62.0% do during the day is look at or check any screen, while 45.9% sometimes feel that the time spent on screen reduces their negative emotions.

Finally, the report showed that 76.8% frequently attempted to control, limit, or reduce the amount of time spent with any screen but were unable to do so, 40.6% rarely lie to relatives (family members, friends, etc.) about the amount of time spent with any screen, and 62.0% always jeopardize various opportunities for their education (inability to prepare for exams (15). A total of 134 students were enrolled for a similar research work done in Jos. There were 80 (59.7%) females and 54 (40.3%) males giving a male to female ratio of 1:1.48. Of the total number of students enrolled for the study, 133 (99.25%) owned a smartphone, while only 1 (0.75%) did not own a smartphone. The major reasons why the students owned smartphones were to keep in touch with family and friends 27.2%, closely followed by academics 25.6%, to pass information 24.7% and entertainment 22.6%. 87 (65.4%) of the students spend more than four hours on their phones daily and only 6 (4.5%) spend less than one hour on their phones. 101 (83.5%) of the students use their smartphones to surf the net daily while only 2 (1.5%) surf the net twice a week. 128 (23.1%) of the 554 multiple responses had Google play store application on their phones, closely followed by 122 (22.0%) having a read document application, the least application was blogging with only thirty one(5.6%) of students having it in their phones. From their responses using the most number of hours spent on sites per week, 10.2% spend >20 hours on academic sites, while 6.0% spend > 20 hours on chatting sites, and 5.7% spend >20 hours on social networking sites per week(18).

2.3 Epidemiology of Internet Addiction Among Medical Students

Different studies have employed different means in administration and assessment of the pattern of mobile device use and possibly its associated internet addiction. The Bergen Facebook Addiction Scale (BFAS) in 2012 was administered by Andreassen et al. using an initial pool of 18 items, three reflecting each of the six core elements of addiction (salience, mood modification, tolerance, withdrawal, conflict and relapse). This was constructed and administered to 423 students, together with several other standardized self-report scales(31). The objective of

these studies has remained the classification of the behavioral patterns associated with problematic mobile device use. The one by Wang classified this as "Yes" and "No" by setting clear boundaries. Another study by Kim et al. which employed the Korean Smartphone Proneness Scale (KSAPS) was composed of 15 items with a 4-point Likert scale(26).

Internet addiction, defined as excessive or poorly controlled preoccupations, urges, or behaviors regarding computer use and internet access that lead to impairment or distress, is an emerging concern among medical students. As expected, there has been a parallel increase of usage of mobile devices and consumption of the internet as well. Just as the number of mobile phone users, the number of monthly active internet users worldwide has risen from just over a million in the fourth quarter of 2013 to over 3 million monthly active users a decade later. This geometrical rise in consumption is consistent with most social media platforms, especially if they have been around for the same number of years(11). A lot of medical students in this regard have become culpable to internet addiction and excessive mobile device use because of their extended stay in schools, demands for online courses, need for soft copies of study materials and textbooks, self therapies with mood stabilizing media, online job deals and commercial platforms like Notcoin to navigate the harsh economic terrains. Cross sectional studies done on Chinese medical students including 36,365 study subjects showed 10,597 (29.14%) cases of mobile phone and internet addiction(32).

To shift our focus to Africa and in particular Nigeria, reviewing a few works from notable institutions like Benue state university, University of Ibadan, Obafemi Awolowo university e.t.c. Nigeria, with a population estimate of about 215 million in 2022, according to United Nations (UN) estimates, has more than 200 million mobile phone (MP) subscribers as of 2020, according to the Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC). Just like the Benue state university students, more than 50% of the 200 University of Ibadan students interviewed in a study by Ezemenaka reported that they have more than 1 phone. Of those who have the internet enabled phones about 97% of them were actively used with internet mobile services to enable them to surf and browse the net. For those that browse 7hrs daily was 87 out of the 200 participants, that is 43.5%, those that fall in between 5 hours daily were 51 with 25.5%, the 3 hours daily were 11 respondents and the percentage is 5.5%, less than 1hr daily were 51 respondents and the percentage is 21.5%. Among the interviewed students on browsing frequency, the respondents

indicated that they browse more on social sites than for academic purposes. This was substantiated by Olson et al.(33) In substantiating the reason for their preference, they indicated that it helps them to cool off during their stay and study in the institution otherwise schooling will be boring for them without connecting to their friends and loved ones. However, most of the respondents browse a minimum of 6 hours intensive daily while some browse and chat at every single available opportunity(2).

2.4 Factors Related to Internet Addiction

Internet addiction has been shown to be influenced by different factors including Individual characteristics, family- and school-related variables, and environmental variables(1). Most previous studies on Internet addiction have often classified the individual factors into genetics, structural brain changes and underlying mental health conditions among other factors(2); those that considered environmental influence typically only examined the proximal environment. Effective prevention and intervention of Internet addiction require a framework that integrates individual- and environmental-level factors.

A study by Chung et al examined the relationships between personal factors, family/school factors, perceived Internet characteristics, and environmental variables as they contribute to Internet addiction among adolescents based on the public health model. A representative sample of 1628 junior high school students from 56 regions in Seoul and Gyeonggi-do participated in the study via questionnaires with the cooperation of the Ministry of Health and Welfare and the district office of education. The study analyzed psychological factors, family cohesion, attitudes toward academic activities, Internet characteristics, accessibility to PC cafés, and exposure to Internet game advertising. About 6% of the adolescents were categorized as being in the severely addicted group. Between-group comparisons showed that the addicted group had started using the Internet earlier; had higher levels of depression, compulsivity, and aggressiveness as well as lower family cohesion; and reported higher accessibility to PC cafés and exposure to Internet game advertising. Multiple logistic regression indicated that for adolescents, environmental factors had a greater influence than family or school-related factors. Policy implications for prevention and intervention are discussed(1).

Another epidemiological study which was done to assess the prevalence of problematic social media use by using scales to screen individuals who suffer from problematic social media use showed that 15.2% of college students in China and 19.9% of college students in India have an excessive mobile device use problem(15). This study was carried out in 2020 across 19 states and showed those at risk represented 20 - 40% of this population. Out of the 1,173 participating college students, the outcome showed that students who reported poorer parent-to-child relationships, higher levels of depression and lower levels of psychosocial competence were more likely to report behaviors indicative of internet addiction(19). These studies have cited college students in general as being the most susceptible given the high neurotic and stressful nature of being a college student. If this is accurate, it is even so more attainable for medical students.

2.5 Effect of Internet Addiction on Academic Performance

Research indicates that internet addiction is prevalent among medical students due to the high demands of their studies and the easy access to online resources. A study conducted by Muhammed et al in 2018 at Ayub Medical College, Abbottabad showed that 11 (7.86%) medical students fulfilled the criteria for internet addiction. Though the mostly recognised reason for purchase of mobile devices for medical students was academic, most of the students 93 (66.3%) used the internet to visit social media applications. Internet addicts performed significantly below average when compared to non-addicts. Internet addiction is more prevalent in females than males (12.5% Vs 2.9%)(24). Presently, different medical devices, ranging from diagnostic tools to educational resources, play vital roles in modern medical education. These devices include laptops, tablets, smartphones, and specialized medical equipment like stethoscopes, x-rays, CT scan and ultrasound machines. These devices are meant to serve as a means of advanced technology that were basically designed to facilitate research and official communications within the academic scope. However, with the passage of time, the use of mobile devices has grown exponentially with ever changing scope of its use has ironically led to a staggering plummet of performances within students(34).

With the objective to study the prevalence and impact of mobile phone use by medical students, 129 students from classes 2nd, 3rd, 4th and 5th years at Oman Medical College responded to a

questionnaire to this effect. The age ranged from 17-24 years; 90.7% females. The results showed that 100% of the students were using a smartphone mobile device. Almost 50% of the students who were mostly females were using the internet and Wi-Fi on mobile for more than 4 hours per day, 87% using headphones(35). Same interview was carried out in Saudi Arabia to elucidate the pattern of use of mobile devices by the students. 141 (81%) used smart devices for studying while 129 (74.1%) for entertainment and 149 (85.6%) for social networking. Most of the participants (n=138, 79.3%) used smart devices for studying lectures while (n=131, 75.3%) in preparing for problem-based learning (PBL) and case discussion (CD). Reading books, preparing seminars, and making notes during lectures were used by 58.6%, 49.4%, and 24.7% respectively. Most students used mainly smart devices in studying at their home (n=120, 69.77) while (n=52, 30.2%) used them at the college. Most participants (n= 86, 49.71%) believed that the smart devices used in studying would improve their academic performance, while (n=9, 5.2%) believed that it had a negative impact on their academic performance. Some participants stated that it has no effect (n=35, 20.23%) on the relation between hours spent studying on smart devices and their academic performance. Most students had an average academic performance (n=92, 52.9%). Students with high, and low academic performance were 36.2% and 10.9% respectively. Nine (47.4%) students with high academic performance study less than three hours/day with smart devices compared to (37.7%), and (30.84%) of the students who study 3-6 and more than 6 hours/ day(23).

CHAPTER THREE

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study Area

The study was carried out in the University of Uyo, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Uyo is the capital of Akwa Ibom state which is the second-largest oil-producing state in the country in the Southern part of Nigeria. It lies within latitudes 5°2'N, and longitudes 7°54'E(36). Uyo became the state capital on September 23, 1987 when Akwa Ibom was created from the then Cross River State(37). According to the 2006 Census, Uyo (including Itu) had a population of 427,873(37). However, the 2022 Revision of World population by United Nations shows the current population of Uyo in 2023 to be 1,329,000(38) Residents mainly speaks Ibibio language, which is the native language of people living in Akwa Ibom State. Other prominent languages spoken includes, Anang, Efik, Igbo, English languages and others.(36)

Uyo is very accessible by road, it also has an international airport, The main attraction of Uyo include local parks, green zones, hotels, restaurants, recreation areas like Ibeno Beach, Lé Meridien Ibom Hotel and Golf Resort, Ibom Connection, Ibom plaza, Godswill Obot Akpabio International Stadium, Unity Park,

Uyo has a rich cultural heritage as manifested in music, festival, arts and crafts and traditional hospitality of the people as well as dressing, the dominant dressing of an Ibibio man is a loincloth “Unwanwang Ofong Isin” and shirt with hat and staff to go with; while the women have a Loincloth as well generally called ‘Ndot Iba’ with a piece of it on the head as head-tie with blouse to match. They are blessed with delicacies such as White soup (Afia Efere), Afang Soup, Edikang Ikong Soup, Ubo Nkong etc. In entertainment, they have various cultural dances

and cultural play like, “Ebre” for women, “Asian Uboikpa” for young girls and also the “Akpara” for women. The men have the “Ekpo” masquerade, the “akinkoriko” or “Awade” for the young boys. Uyo has the largest deposits of Crude oil. The people of Uyo are predominantly farmers and traders.(39)

3.2 Study location

The University of Uyo is located in Uyo, the capital of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The university was formerly known as the University of Cross River State, with 1,521 Academic staff, 4,128 Administrative staff, 127,980 Undergraduates, 30,334 Postgraduates.(40)

The University of Uyo has 14 faculties, the postgraduate school and the school of Continuing Education.(41)

The institution operates on four campuses;

1. The Permanent Site/Main Campus, which houses the Central Administration, Engineering, Natural and Applied Sciences, and Agriculture faculties, as well as the International Centre for Energy and Environmental Sustainability Research (ICEESR) and Postgraduate School.
2. The Town Campus houses the faculties of arts, education, social sciences, and pharmacy.
3. The Annex Campus is home to Business Administration, Law, Environmental Studies, and General Studies.
4. The Ime Umana Campus in Ediene Abak houses the Pre-Degree, JUPEB, and other specific courses.(42)

Medical students, when admitted into the university, are students of the College of Health Sciences. The college has four faculties (Basic medical, Allied health science, Basic clinical and Clinical sciences). The medical students pass through the four faculties in the course of the study.

These students, in first year, have their classes in town campus, annex campus and main campus. The pre-clinical classes attend lectures in annex campus while the clinical classes have their lectures and clinical rotations in the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital. The estimated number of medical students in the University of Uyo College of Health Sciences is 920 students.

3.3 Study Design

This study was a descriptive cross-sectional study of all medical students in University of Uyo, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

3.4 Study Population

The study population in this research included all bonafide medical students from year one (1) to year six (6) in the University of Uyo, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. All medical students in the university of Uyo had an equal chance of being in the study

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Students who refused to give their consent
2. Medical students who were currently not in the school during the period of the research.

3.5 Sample Size Determination

The estimated population of all medical students was 920 as obtained from the various class attendance lists. The minimum sample size was determined assuming the prevalence of addiction among undergraduate medical students in University of Uyo to be 50%, using the Cochran formula.

$$n = z^2pq / d^2$$

Where,

n = calculated sample size

z = 1.96(standard deviation corresponding to 95% confidence interval)

p = 0.5(assumed prevalence 50%)

q = 1 - 0.5 = 0.5

d = 0.05 (margin of error)

$$[(1.96)^2 \times 0.5 \times 0.5] / 0.05^2$$

$$n \text{ (calculated sample size)} = 384$$

As this was not an infinite population, the sample size has to be adjusted to reflect the estimated population.

- Adjusted sample size = $n/(1 + n/N)$

Where,

n = calculated sample size

N = Estimated population size

- Adjusted sample size = 270

Non-response rate = 10%

10% x 270 = 27

- Final sample size = 270 + 27.0 = 297

3.6 Sampling Technique

A stratified sampling (proportionate sampling) size using proportional allocation was used to select respondents from each level of study

Year 1	250	$(250/920) \times 297 = 80.7$	81
Year 2	154	$(154/920) \times 297 = 49.7$	50
Year 4a	110	$(110/920) \times 297 = 35.5$	36
Year 4b	96	$(96/920) \times 297 = 30.99$	31
Year 5a	110	$(110/920) \times 297 = 35.5$	36
Year 5b	100	$(100/920) \times 297 = 32.29$	32
Year 6	100	$(100/920) \times 297 = 32.28$	32

The eligible participants were selected by systematic sampling technique after a proportionate allocation of the number of participants to be selected from each of the six classes/levels of training was done. This was done till the sample size of 297 was obtained.

3.7 Data Collection Tools

The questionnaire used was the structured questionnaire. This questionnaire was adapted from the Internet Addiction Test by Dr. Kimberly Young (43) to assess the level of internet addiction amongst Medical Students in University of Uyo. Having a final population size of 297, this number of questionnaires was distributed to the medical students across the different classes. The questionnaire had 5 sections:

Section A consisted of demographic information

Section B consisted of pattern of mobile usage

Section C assessed internet addiction adapted from Kimberly Young

Section D was for other relevant questions

Section E has additional information.

We utilized validated tools such as the Internet Addiction Test (IAT) by Dr. Kimberly Young to assess levels of internet addiction.

3.8 Data Collection Techniques

Questionnaires were administered to the participants using trained research assistants between July and August 2024. Two(2) research assistants helped administer the questionnaires across the various years of study using an Open Data Kit (ODK) software and Google form from July to August 2024.

3.9 Data Collection Procedures

The interviewer-administered questionnaire was shared among the Medical Students of University of Uyo. The researchers approached individual students of each of the eligible classes, provided access to the data link and explained in detail the requirements, sequences and steps involved. On filling the questionnaire, they were all submitted via the software and recorded.

3.10 Data Analysis

Data was analyzed using the STAT Version 16 software package. The Young's Internet Addiction Test is a 20-item questionnaire rated on a 5-point scale ranging from 0 to 5, with a minimum total score of 0, and a maximum total score of 100. Total scores of 0 to 30 is regarded as normal internet usage, total scores of 31 to 49 as a mild level of internet addiction, total scores of 50 to 79 indicates a moderate level of internet addiction, while total scores of 80 to 100 indicates a severe dependence on the internet (43). Quantitative variables were summarized using mean and standard deviation, while categorical variables were summarized using frequencies and percentages. Chi Square analysis was used to determine the factors that were associated with internet addiction. The level of significance chosen was set at 5%.

3.11 Ethical Consideration

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee of the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital and digital informed consent was taken from each participant. An Information Consent Section was contained in the questionnaire for the participants. The purpose of the study was clearly explained to the respondents. They were assured that no time or place will be associated with their responses, and their names were not required. They were told that they are free to decline answering any questions that they do not feel like providing answers to. Confidentiality was assured by giving them clear and accurate statements about confidentiality during data collection. To secure privacy of participants, names and other means of identification were not used during the research. Instead, the questionnaires were given identification numbers. The expected duration of the interview was about 30 minutes and this was explained to the respondents. The participants were informed that the study will not

expose them to any risk; and was also aimed at improving their knowledge on the pattern of mobile device usage and internet addiction among medical students at no cost to them.

3.12 Limitation of Study

Some limitations of the study included:

1. **Self-Reporting of Data:** This study relied on self-reported data, which may be subject to some form of biases such as recall bias, social desirability bias, or inaccuracies.
2. **Study Design:** The study design was a cross-sectional study, which only provided a snapshot of the situation at a given point in time, making the study difficult to infer causation or observe changes over time.
3. **Small sample size:** If the sample size was not an adequate representation of the larger population of medical students, the findings from the study might not be generalizable.
4. **Confounding Variables:** There might be confounding variables which could not be controlled such as: the students' workload, emotional state, stress levels and other personal factors that could influence mobile device usage and internet addiction.

CHAPTER 4 RESULT

A total of 297 medical students were recruited for the study, 47% (140/297) of the respondents are female. The results of the analysis are presented below in tables and charts.

Table 1: Socio demographic characteristics of the respondents

Variables	Sex n (%)		Statistical indices
	Female(n=140)	Male (n=157)	
Age (years)			
15-19	49 (53.3)	43 (46.7)	P value=0.002+*
20-24	78 (51.0)	75 (49.0)	
25-29	13 (28.3)	33 (71.7)	
30 and above	0 (0.0)	6 (100.0)	
Mean (SD)	20.8 (2.7)	22.3 (3.6)	Df=295 Tt=-4.085 P value=0.0001+
Year of study			
2	41 (50.6)	40 (49.4)	Df=6 X ² =4.342 P value=0.631
3	21 (46.7)	24 (53.3)	
4A	19 (50.0)	19 (50.0)	
4B	19 (57.6)	14 (42.4)	
5	11 (37.9)	18 (62.1)	
6	17 (43.6)	22 (56.4)	
7	12 (37.5)	20 (62.5)	
Living arrangement			Df=1
Off campus	39 (30.7)	88 (69.3)	X ² =24.035
On campus	101 (59.4)	69 (40.6)	P value>0.0001+
Average screen time per			

day	2 (66.7)	1 (33.3)	P value=0.017+*
Less than 1	17 (70.8)	7 (29.2)	
1-3 hours	25 (47.2)	28 (52.8)	
3-5 hours	49 (52.7)	44 (47.3)	
5-7 hours	47 (37.9)	77 (62.1)	
Above 7 hours			

+ sig P value; *Fischer's exacttest

Table 1 shows that the female respondents are significantly younger than their male counterparts, the proportion of females who live on campus are significantly higher than the proportion of males and the average screen time for males is higher than females. There is no difference between the year of study among the two sexes.

Fig.1: Mobile devices used by the respondents

Fig.1 shows that 96.6 % of the respondents used smartphones, 35.7% used laptops and 6.7% on tablets

Fig.2: Main activities on mobile device by the respondents

Fig.2 shows that the most important activity is on mobile device is academic activity, messaging or social media is the least of about 75%

Fig.3 : Use of social platform among the respondents

Fig 3 shows that Whatsapp is the most commonly used platform (89%), followed by Facebook and Instagram

Table 2a: Assessment of internet addiction among male and female respondents

Variables	Rarely 1	Occasional 2	Sometim es 3	Often 4	Always 5	Average score
How often do you stay on the internet more than you intended Male Female	16 (69.6) 7 (30.4)	41 (55.4) 33 (44.6)	43 (53.1) 38 (46.9)	27 (42.2) 37 (57.8)	30 (54.5) 25 (45.5)	3.1 3.3 P value=0.166
How often do you neglect household chores to spend time online Male Female	27 (45.0) 33 (55.0)	57 (55.9) 45 (44.1)	27 (46.6) 31 (53.4)	30 (58.8) 21 (41.2)	16 (61.5) 10 (38.5)	2.7 2.5 P value=0.190
How often do you prefer the excitement of the internet to spending						

time with your partner/family?						
Male	32 (51.6)	36 (54.6) 30 (45.4)	33 (50.0) 33 (50.0)	27 (51.9)	29 (56.9)	2.9 2.8
Female	30 (48.4)			25 (48.1)	22 (43.1)	P value=0.723
How often do you form relationship with other online users						
Male	69 (46.6)	43 (53.8) 39 (46.2)	21 (60.0) 14 (40.0)	16 (72.7)	8 (66.7)	2.0 1.7
Female	79 (53.4)			6 (27.3)	4 (33.3)	P value=0.008+
How often do your school work suffer because of the amount of time you spend online?						
Male	86 (51.2)	40 (49.4) 41 (50.6)	20 (64.5) 11 (35.5)	9 (64.3) 5 (35.7)	2 (66.7)	1.6 1.7
Female	82 (48.8)				1 (33.3)	P value=0.168
How often do you find yourself anticipating when you will go online again?						
Male	67 (51.5)	37 (58.7) 26 (41.3)	21 (48.8) 22 (51.2)	20 (60.6)	12 (42.9)	2.2 2.2
Female	63 (48.5)			13 (39.4)	16 (57.1)	P value=0.778
How often do others in your life complain to you about the time you spend online?						
Male	78 (49.7)	41 (59.4) 28 (40.6)	19 (52.8) 17 (47.2)	15 (62.5)	4 (36.4)	1.9 1.8
Female	79 (50.3)			9 (37.5)	7 (63.6)	P value=0.673
How often do you check your email before something else that you need to do?						
Male	67 (48.2)	34 (61.8) 21 (38.2)	26 (57.8) 19 (42.2)	11 (39.3)	19 (63.3)	2.2 2.1
Female	72 (51.8)			17 (60.7)	11 (36.7)	P value=0.374

Table 2a shows that male respondents are more likely to form relationship online more than females, other variables are similar in both sexes

Table 2b: Assessment of internet addiction among male and female respondents

Variables	Rarely 1	Occasiona lly 2	Sometim es 3	Often 4	Always 5	Average score
How often does your reading and studies or productivity suffer because of the Internet? Male Female	64 (52.5) 58 (47.5)	37 (47.4) 41 (52.6)	30 (52.6) 27 (47.4)	17 (63.0) 10 (37.0)	9 (69.2) 4 (30.8)	2.2 2.0 P value =0.224
How often do you become defensive or secretive when anyone asks you what you do on-line? Male Female	97 (51.0) 93 (49.0)	30 (51.7) 28 (48.3)	17 (70.8) 7 (29.2)	7 (43.8) 9 (56.2)	6 (66.7) 3 (33.3)	1.7 1.6 P value=0.340
How often do you block out disturbing thoughts about your life with soothing thoughts of the Internet? Male Female	63 (55.8) 50 (44.2)	33 (56.9) 25 (43.1)	31 (56.4) 24 (43.6)	18 (40.0) 27 (60.0)	12 (46.2) 14 (53.8)	2.5 2.2 P value=0.119
How often do you fear that life without the Internet would be boring, empty, and joyless? Male Female	49 (50.0) 49 (50.0)	28 (50.0) 28 (50.0)	22 (50.0) 22 (50.0)	29 (69.0) 13 (31.0)	29 (50.9) 28 (49.1)	2.8 2.6 P value=0.371
How often do you snap, yell, or act annoyed if someone bothers you while you are on-line? Male Female	104 (55.9) 82 (44.1)	30 (50.8) 29 (49.2)	13 (46.4) 15 (53.6)	7 (41.2) 10 (58.8)	3 (42.9) 4 (57.1)	1.6 1.8 P

						value=0.124
How often do you lose sleep due to late-night Mobile Device and Internet usage?						
Male	47 (48.4)	35 (52.2)	30 (60.0)	27 (52.9)	18 (56.2)	2.6
Female	50 (51.6)	32 (47.8)	20 (40.0)	24 (47.1)	14 (43.8)	2.4
						P value=0.347
How often do you feel preoccupied with the Internet when off-line, or fantasize about being on-line?						
Male	75 (48.1)	43 (56.6)	19 (59.4)	14 (63.6)	6 (54.6)	1.9
Female	81 (51.9)	33 (43.4)	13 (40.6)	8 (36.4)	5 (45.4)	1.7
						P value=0.122

Table 2b shows that all the variables for assessment of internet addiction are similar in both sexes

Table 2c: Assessment of internet addiction among male and female respondents

Variables	Rarely 1	Occasional 2	Sometim es 3	Often 4	Always 5	Average score
How often do you find yourself saying “just a few more minutes” when on-line?						
Male	46 (68.7)	31 (53.4) 27 (46.6)	39 (49.4) 40 (50.6)	24 (43.6)	17 (44.7)	2.6
Female	21 (31.3)			31 (56.4)	21 (55.3)	3.0
						P value=0.004+
How often do you try to cut down the amount of time you spend on-line and fail?						
Male	46 (56.1)	33 (51.6) 31 (48.4)	38 (56.7) 29 (43.3)	28 (45.2)	12 (54.6)	2.5
Female	36 (43.9)			34 (54.8)	10 (45.4)	2.6
						P value=0.444
How often do you try to hide how long						

you've been on-line?	87 (54.0)	24 (38.7) 38 (61.3)	17 (58.6) 12 (41.4)	15 (60.0)	14 (70.0)	2.0 1.8
Male						
Female	74 (46.0)			10 (40.0)	6 (30.0)	P value=0.208
How often do you choose to spend more time on-line over going out with others?						
Male	56 (56.0)	33 (62.3) 20 (37.7)	33 (61.1) 21 (38.9)	17 (36.2)	18 (41.9)	2.4 2.8
Female	44 (44.0)			30 (63.8)	25 (58.1)	P value=0.022+
How often do you feel depressed, moody, or nervous when you are off-line, which goes away once you are back on-line?						
Male	86 (53.1)	32 (55.2) 26 (44.8)	19 (50.0) 19 (50.0)	5 (31.2) 11 (68.8)	15 (65.2)	1.9 1.9
Female	76 (46.9)				8 (34.8)	P value=0.988

Table 2c shows that female are more likely to "say just a few more minute when on line" and prefer to spend more time online than their male counterparts

Fig. 4: level of Internet addiction among the respondents

Fig.4 shows that 18.5% of the respondents have no addiction, 46.5% have mild addiction, 34% have moderate addiction and only 1% has severe addiction

Table 3: Mean internet addiction score among the respondent by sex

Internet score	Sex n (%)		Total (n=297)	Statistical indices
	Male (n=157)	Female (n=140)		
Mean (SD)	45.2 (14.7)	44.9 (14.1)	45.1(14.4)	Df=295 Tt=-0.176 P value=0.860

Table 4: Factors associated with internet addiction among the respondents

Variables	Level of addiction n (%)		Statistical indices
	Normal (n=55)	Addiction (n=106)	
Gender Male Female	27 (17.2) 28 (20.0)	130 (82.8) 112 (80.0)	Df=1 X ² =0.385 P value=0.526
Age (years) 15-19 20-24 25-29 30 and above Mean (SD)	14 (15.2) 31 (20.3) 8 (17.4) 2 (33.3) 22.0 (3.4)	78 (84.8) 122 (79.7) 38 (82.6) 4 (66.7) 21.5 (3.3)	df=2 X ² =1.884 P value=0.584 Df=295 Tt=1.080 P value=0.281
Year of study 2 3 4a 4b 5 6a 6b	14 (17.3) 5 (11.1) 7 (18.4) 7 (21.2) 4 (13.8) 11 (28.2) 7 (21.9)	67 (82.7) 40 (88.9) 31 (81.6) 26 (78.8) 25 (86.2) 28 (71.8) 25 (78.1)	P value=0.554
Living arrangement Off campus On campus	26 (20.5) 29 (17.1)	101 (79.5) 141 (82.9)	Df=1 X ² =0.561 P value=0.454
Average screen time Less than 1 hour 1-3 hours 3-5 hours 5-7 hours More than 7 hours	1 (33.3) 13 (54.2) 10 (18.9) 20 (21.5) 11 (8.9)	2 (66.7) 11 (45.8) 43 (81.1) 73 (78.5) 113 (91.1)	P value>0.0001+*

+ significant P value; *Fischer's exact test

Table 4 shows that age, gender, level of study and living arrangement do not have any relationship with internet addiction among the medical students. However, the average screen time is very strongly related with addiction.

Table 5: The perceived effects of level of internet addiction on academic performance and study time of the respondents

Variables	Level of addiction n (%)		Statistical indices
	Normal (n=55)	Addiction (n=106)	
Do you think this has affected your Academic performance in School? Yes No Maybe	2 (4.1) 36 (26.1) 17 (15.4)	47 (95.9) 102 (73.9) 93 (84.6)	P value=0.001+*
Does the use of Mobile Devices interfere with your study time? Yes No Maybe	10 (7.2) 30 (36.1) 15 (20.0)	129 (92.8) 53 (63.9) 60 (80.0)	Df=2 X=29.012 P Value <0.0001+
Has it Negatively affected your results? Yes No	0 (0.0) 47 (24.7) 8 (11.0)	34 (100.0) 143 (75.3) 65 (89.0)	P value< 0.0001+*

Maybe			

+ sig. p value, *Fischer's exact test

Table 5 shows that students who think internet use affect their academic performance has significantly higher proportion of addiction compared to those who do not think so, those who say internet use interfere with their study time also have significantly higher proportion of addiction compared to those who are not, all the students who think internet have negatively affected their result have internet addiction.

CHAPTER 5

DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Discussion

This study provides insights into the patterns of internet addiction and mobile usage behaviors among medical students, highlighting key factors such as demographics, screen time, and academic impacts. Female students are significantly younger on average than their male counterparts, and a higher proportion of female students reside on campus. Males, however, report a notably higher average screen time than females. This pattern aligns with research by

Wacks (17) which found that younger individuals and students residing on campus often have more structured schedules, potentially influencing internet usage.

The higher screen time among male students also echoes findings by Kim et al. (26), who reported that males are more likely to exhibit increased screen time, often linked to gaming and online social activities. This result highlights the gender-specific patterns of internet usage, indicating that males may be more inclined toward online entertainment, while females tend to use the internet primarily for academic purposes and social interactions.

This study shows that 96.6% of respondents use smartphones, 35.7% use laptops, with only 6.7% using tablets. This high smartphone prevalence is similar to findings by Amaez et al.(34), who noted the centrality of smartphones in academic and social activities among students. The comparatively lower usage of laptops and tablets may indicate the convenience of smartphones as all-in-one devices for accessing information, connecting socially, and managing academic work. The high smartphone usage underscores the potential for mobile devices to contribute to addiction, as the constant accessibility can lead to habitual or even compulsive internet use (34).

Academic activity is the primary reason for the use of mobile devices among respondents, with a lower proportion engaged in messaging or social media. This finding, where academic activity is the primary reason for device use among students, differs from a study by Zenebe et al(32), which observed that social media was typically the most common activity on mobile devices among students in general. The dominance of academic use here suggests that the academic rigor of medical training may be driving students to prioritize studies over social interactions online. This trend highlights the dual role of mobile devices as both academic tools and sources of potential distraction, depending on usage patterns.

WhatsApp is the most frequently used platform (89%), followed by Facebook and Instagram. This preference for WhatsApp aligns with findings by Olson et al(33), which emphasized WhatsApp's popularity for communication within academic environments due to its ease of use and group chat functions. Compared to other platforms, WhatsApp supports both formal and informal communication, making it versatile for academic group discussions and social interaction. The data implies that while social media can contribute to internet addiction, the

specific choice of platform may also relate to academic convenience and peer connectivity, thus influencing addiction levels.

Findings from this study shows that males form online relationships more frequently, whereas females are more likely to extend their time online, often losing track of time. This pattern aligns with studies by Hong et al (29), which noted that males often engage in social networking to expand connections, while females tend to become more absorbed in specific tasks, such as extended browsing or academic activities. The gender difference here emphasizes the importance of understanding distinct addictive behaviors across demographics, suggesting that targeted interventions might be needed to address specific usage patterns.

Most internet addiction behaviors do not significantly differ between sexes, except in cases where females tend to "stay just a few more minutes" and prefer online engagement over offline social activities. This result aligns with Hamval et al(14), who identified time distortion and neglect of offline relationships as key signs of internet addiction. The lack of significant differences in most behaviors between males and females suggests that while some tendencies vary, the risk of addiction is prevalent across both genders. This highlights the need for a universal approach to managing internet addiction, with tailored strategies for behaviors like time distortion that might be more prominent in females.

The prevalence of internet addiction in this study is 81.5%, with 46.5% having mild addiction, 34% moderate addiction, and only 1% severe addiction. This distribution aligns with findings from studies by Ayindele et al. (44), which report that mild to moderate addiction levels are more common among students, with severe cases being rare. The moderate levels of addiction could be attributed to the academic and social demands placed on students, leading them to rely on the internet for both study resources and social interaction. With the internet being a primary tool for educational research, social media, and leisure, it's common for students to develop habits that approach moderate addiction levels, especially given the increased screen time required in modern academic environments. The relatively low rate of severe addiction may be due to a combination of factors: a level of self-regulation among students, possible awareness of the risks of excessive internet use, and academic obligations that limit internet use primarily to study-related activities. However, the high prevalence of moderate addiction suggests that

without proper guidance or intervention, such as awareness programs, students could experience interference with their academic performance and mental well-being.

This distribution indicates that while severe addiction is not widespread, a substantial proportion of students still experience moderate levels of addiction that could impact their daily routines. This suggests that mild interventions, such as awareness programs or digital literacy courses, could be effective in managing addiction levels and preventing escalation.

There is no significant difference in mean internet addiction scores between males and females. This is consistent with studies by Ajayi, Owolabi, and Olajire(45), which have shown that while behaviors may vary, addiction scores often show no significant gender bias. This finding implies that while males and females may engage differently with the internet, both genders are equally susceptible to addictive behaviors.

The results of table 4 demonstrate that variables like gender, year of study, and living arrangement show no strong association to internet addiction. Although it appears that a lower rate of addiction was noticed in students aged 30 years and above (66.7%) as against a mean of 82.4% across other age groups, this has no significant relationship to internet addiction but seems to be due to a cognitive bias of small numbers. However, the results shows that the association between the average screen time and internet addiction among students is over 91% as they spend more than 7 hours on their screens. Furthermore, only 2 students who were addicted to the internet spent less than an hour per day as their average screen time. This agrees with studies by Otinwa and Ademola(46), which found screen time to be the most predictive factor for internet addiction, emphasizing the need to manage screen exposure as a preventive strategy. The lack of association with demographic variables like gender, year of study and living arrangements suggests that addiction is a more behavior-driven phenomenon rather than one linked to inherent demographic factors.

Table 5 highlights that students who perceive internet use as detrimental to their academic performance are more likely to exhibit addiction symptoms. This is in line with studies by Afolabi, Ilesanmi, and Adebayo(47), which observed a strong negative correlation between internet addiction and academic success. The data underscores the cyclical nature of addiction,

where internet use impacts academic outcomes, leading to stress that may further drive addictive behaviors. This finding highlights the importance of addressing internet addiction not only to improve academic performance but also to support students' mental well-being.

5.2 Conclusion

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of internet addiction among medical students, revealing patterns that align closely with similar findings in academic settings. A significant proportion (81.5%) of the students were identified with varying levels of addiction, with the majority exhibiting mild to moderate forms and only 1% experiencing severe addiction. This indicates that, while not pervasive, addiction remains a substantial issue that could impact the well-being and academic performance of students if not addressed. The patterns in mobile device use further show a strong preference for smartphones, with academic activities emerging as the primary use. Gender-specific tendencies in screen time were observed, with males demonstrating a greater inclination toward online entertainment, while females leaned more towards academic and social internet use. Internet addiction is associated with screen time. The main effect of internet addiction is poor academic performance.

5.3 Recommendations

Given the high prevalence of moderate internet addiction, this study recommends

1. Implementing awareness programs and digital literacy courses within the medical curriculum to educate students on managing screen time effectively. Such programs should emphasize the risks of excessive use and strategies for balanced, mindful internet consumption.
2. Considering the high smartphone usage for academic purposes, encouraging students to establish screen time limits may help mitigate compulsive internet use.
3. Gender-specific interventions could also be beneficial, with males potentially targeted with resources on managing gaming and entertainment use and females encouraged to monitor time spent on academic browsing to avoid overuse.

4. Faculty could support students with alternative resources like digital detox initiatives and study support programs that reduce the need for extended screen use.
5. Periodic assessments of internet use and addiction among students could help identify trends early, enabling timely intervention to prevent escalation to severe addiction levels.

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APPENDIX
INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Study: Patterns of Mobile Device Usage and Internet Addiction among Medical Students at University of Uyo.

Investigators:

Ekpo, Etinkpo Anthony

Robert, Edidiong Peter

Ezekiel, Ofofon-Ono Enefiok

Egwu, Henry Amarachukwu

Gobo, Obubelebara Rose

Sagbara, Barida Charles

Ekpe, Miracle Eyo

Umoh, Ekwere Nsima

Contact Information: 0815 137 8732, robertedidiong0@gmail.com

Introduction:

You are invited to participate in a research study conducted by the above listed final year medical students at the University of Uyo, as part of the requirements for the award of MBBS. Please read the following information carefully before deciding whether to participate in this study.

Purpose:

The purpose of this study is to investigate the patterns of mobile device usage and the incidence of internet addiction among medical students at the University of Uyo. The study aims to understand how these factors may impact academic achievement and overall well-being among students.

Procedures:

If you agree to participate, you will be asked to complete a structured questionnaire administered by trained research assistants. The questionnaire includes sections on demographics, patterns of mobile device usage, and an assessment of internet addiction using the Internet Addiction Test (IAT) adapted from Dr. Kimberly Young's tool. The questionnaire will be administered using Open Data Kit (ODK) software, ensuring efficient data collection and minimizing questionnaire wastage.

Risks and Benefits:

There are minimal anticipated risks associated with participating in this study. Some questions may prompt you to reflect on your personal internet usage, which could potentially cause mild discomfort. However, this will be minimized by ensuring confidentiality and anonymity of your responses. The benefits of participating include contributing to research that may help improve understanding and support for medical students regarding mobile device usage and internet addiction.

Confidentiality:

Your participation in this study is confidential. Your responses will be anonymized, and only aggregate data will be reported. All data will be stored securely and will only be accessible to the research team. No personally identifiable information will be included in any reports or publications resulting from this study.

Voluntary Participation and Withdrawal:

Participation in this study is voluntary. You have the right to refuse to participate or withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. Your decision will not affect your academic standing or any other aspect of your relationship with the University of Uyo.

Contact Information:

If you have any questions or concerns about the study, you may contact Edidiong Robert at 0815 137 8732, robertedidiong0@gmail.com

Consent:

By clicking "Agree" or submitting the completed questionnaire, you indicate that you voluntarily agree to participate in this study and that you have read and understood the information provided in this consent form.

Date: _____

SAMPLE OF A SURVEY

Survey on Mobile Device Usage and Internet Addiction among Medical Students of University of Uyo

A sample survey form is designed to acquire information on mobile device usage and internet addiction among medical students at the University of Uyo. The survey is divided into several sections to cover

- I. demographic information,
- Ii. mobile device usage patterns,
- Iii. internet addiction assessment.

Introduction

The purpose of this study is to understand the patterns of mobile device usage and the extent of internet addiction among medical students at the University of Uyo.

Anonymous responses will be needed and used for research purposes only.

Sample of a Questionnaire

Questionnaire on Mobile Device Usage and Internet Addiction Among Medical Students

This is a detailed questionnaire form designed to investigate mobile device usage and internet addiction among medical students at the University of Uyo. This form includes various question types to gather comprehensive data.

Introduction

Thank you for taking part in this study. We aim to understand the patterns of mobile device usage and the extent of internet addiction among medical students at the University of Uyo. Your responses are **anonymous** and will only be used for research purposes.

SECTION A: DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

1. Age as at the last birthday: _____

2. Gender:

Male| Female| Prefer not to say

3. Year of Study:

Year 1 |Year 2 |Year 3| Year 4| Year 5| Year 6

4. Living Arrangement:

On-campus| Off-campus

SECTION B: MOBILE DEVICE USAGE PATTERNS

1. Type of Mobile Device Used (select all that apply):

Smartphone| Tablet| Laptop| Other (please specify): _____

2. Average Daily Screen Time on Mobile Devices:

Less than 1 hour| 1-3 hours| 3-5 hours| 5-7 hours| More than 7 hours

3. Main Activities on Mobile Devices (select all that apply):

Social Media (e.g., Facebook, Instagram)| Messaging (e.g., WhatsApp, Telegram)| Browsing the Internet| Watching Videos (e.g., YouTube, Netflix)| Gaming| Studying/Academic Purposes| Other (please specify): _____

4. Most Frequently Used Social Media Platforms (select all that apply):

Facebook| Instagram| Twitter| WhatsApp| TikTok| Snapchat| Other (please specify): _____

SECTION C: INTERNET ADDICTION ASSESSMENT

1. How often do you find that you stay on-line longer than you intended?

1 2 3 4 5 0

2. How often do you neglect your studies to spend more time on-line?

1 2 3 4 5 0

3. How often do you prefer the excitement of the Internet to sitting down to study?

1 2 3 4 5 0

4. How often do you form new relationships with fellow on-line users?

1 2 3 4 5 0

5. How often do others in your life complain to you about the amount of time you spend on-line?

1 2 3 4 5 0

6. How often do your grades or schoolwork suffer because of the amount of time you spend on-line?

1 2 3 4 5 0

7. How often do you check your email before something else that you need to do?

1 2 3 4 5 0

8. How often does your reading and studies or productivity suffer because of the Internet?

1 2 3 4 5 0

9. How often do you become defensive or secretive when anyone asks you what you do on-line?

1 2 3 4 5 0

10. How often do you block out disturbing thoughts about your life with soothing thoughts of the Internet?

1 2 3 4 5 0

11. How often do you find yourself anticipating when you will go on-line again?

1 2 3 4 5 0

12. How often do you fear that life without the Internet would be boring, empty, and joyless?

1 2 3 4 5 0

13. How often do you snap, yell, or act annoyed if someone bothers you while you are on-line?

1 2 3 4 5 0

14. How often do you lose sleep due to late-night Mobile Device and Internet usage?

1 2 3 4 5 0

15. How often do you feel preoccupied with the Internet when off-line, or fantasize about being on-line?

1 2 3 4 5 0

16. How often do you find yourself saying “just a few more minutes” when on-line?

1 2 3 4 5 0

17. How often do you try to cut down the amount of time you spend on-line and fail?

1 2 3 4 5 0

18. How often do you try to hide how long you’ve been on-line?

1 2 3 4 5 0

19. How often do you choose to spend more time on-line over going out with others?

1 2 3 4 5 0

20. How often do you feel depressed, moody, or nervous when you are off-line, which goes away once you are back on-line?

1 2 3 4 5 0

21. How often do you stay online because you feel it is a hobby?

1 2 3 4 5 0

22. How often do family problems and stress make you spend more time online?

1 2 3 4 5 0

23. How often does being online reduce your anxiety, depression and irritability

1 2 3 4 5 0

24. How often does school related stress compel you to go online?

1 2 3 4 5 0

25. How often does affordability and accessibility of data and network make you spend more time online

1 2 3 4 5 0

SECTION D: OTHERS

1. Do you think this has affected your Academic performance in School?

Yes| No| Always| Maybe

2. Does the use of Mobile Devices interfere with your study time?

Yes| No| Always| Maybe

3. Has it Negatively affected your results?

Yes| No| Always| Maybe

SECTION E: ADDITIONAL COMMENTS

1. Do you have any additional comments or suggestions regarding mobile device usage and internet addiction?

Thank you for completing this survey. Your responses are valuable and will contribute significantly to our research.

This survey can be distributed online or in paper format, depending on the preferred method of data collection. Making sure that the test survey was done with a small group before full deployment to ensure clarity and relevance of the questions.

Thank you for completing this questionnaire. Your responses are valuable and will significantly contribute to our research.